

Location, Factors and Objectives in Road-side Units deployment -Analytic study-

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Abstract— Roadside units (RSUs), very positive addition in VANETs that improve performance and efficiency. However, deploying RSUs is a complex task due to various factors and constraints, including installation and maintenance costs, coverage area, communication delay, reliability, network topology, and traffic patterns. Researchers have proposed different methods to optimize RSU placement and achieve specific goals. These optimization algorithms consider multiple factors to ensure effective deployment. In our study, we categorize deployment factors and analyze related work to extract meaningful relationships between factors, objectives, and locations, and gives proposals for future works.

Keywords— VANET, RSU, Deployment, Communication range, Objective function.

I. INTRODUCTION

Vehicle-to-Vehicle communication networks (VANETs) represent a multifaceted field of research that has captivated scholars and academic communities for years. If the focus lies in deploying infrastructure within this domain, researchers discover an ongoing quest for optimal solutions. The challenge lies in strategically placing Roadside Units (RSUs), considering their substantial cost and spatial limitations. Opinions diverge among researchers regarding RSU locations. Some researchers believed that placing the RSU should only be at intersections [1], as other said that it should be placed in the road section because it has no importance at intersections [2], while others saw that the deployment process could be in distinct places [3]. This study presents a comprehensive overview of the underlying factors driving RSU placement and try to find the relation between objectives, locations and factors, Section 2 delves into prior work on placement processes, followed by a discussion of factor types in Section 3. Section 4 presents a comparative analysis of deployment approaches considering objectives, locations, and influencing factors, finished by a scheme that shows the relationship between them. Finally, Section 5 gives the limitations of our study. We conclude with future research proposals.

II. RELATED WORK

Trying to find an effective solution for RSU deployment is a big challenge for specialists in this field, in [4] they wanted to improve delay-sensitive applications, by taking in consideration two types of communication (V2I and V2V) using genetic algorithms to find best positions based on

traffic factor as vehicle arrival rate and connectivity probability in each road-segment, the authors in [5] addresses the problem by modeling it as a 0-1 knapsack problem by taking the centrality as value and the cost as weight, they relied on intersections as candidate positions and neglected remote areas, in [6] they want to minimize the number of RSUs for message dissemination in bounded delay, by taking intersection as candidate position based on traffic flow density, communication range and length as factors, others in [7] saw that the effectiveness of RSU to minimize the delay is to place them in road-segment with low traffic flow, to maximize the coverage the authors in [3] propose a geometric approach called Constrained Delaunay Triangulation (CDT) with only V2I communication used and RSUs take places in distinct locations. In [8] To resolve the D1RD issue, the proposed solution involves an optimal algorithm known as OptDynLim at point with high profit density, to maximize the coverage area the authors in [9] use a hybrid genetic algorithm with local search replacement, a multi-objective roadside deployment model is presented in both of [10] and [11] to maximize the coverage based on overlapping area as factor and reduce the expected transmission delay with limited cost at intersection using V2V and V2I communication and choose NSGA2, memetic algorithm as optimization method respectively, for safety application with threshold delay the authors in [12] they divide the map in region of interest characterized by accident rate factor, in [13] using a genetic algorithm and relying in road-segment with big number of bus stop, high commercial activity and total accident as factors in order to reduce reception delay of safety message delivered from the vehicles, for applications operating in real-time that necessitate minimum latency and rapid data transmission speeds, in [14] they apply a mmwave technology beam antennas and define the issue as the Maximum Coverage under limited financial plan, aiming to optimize profit within the limits of a budget constraint, to ensure maximum coverage of high accident In [15] they use (V2V and V2I) communications and choose road-segment with low connectivity as best positions to deploy a fixed number of RSU

III. DEPLOYMENT FACTORS

After reviewing several research works related to the placement of RSUs, we can divide the factors that the researchers relied on into different types of factors.

A. Network factors:

- Communication range:

In Intelligent Transport Systems, it's the region within which Roadside Units (RSUs) and On-Board Units (OBUs) can effectively communicate with each other[16]. The exact range can vary based on several factors, including the technology used, the environment, and the specific hardware and software implementations, the Fig1 shows the communication range of two RSU and the interference area between them called overlap area.

Fig1. Communication range and overlap area

- Betweenness Centrality:

Measures a node's significance in a graph by assessing its function in the shortest pathways connecting other nodes. This metric indicates which nodes serve as bridges inside a network [17].

The betweenness centrality of a node (v) is defined by the following equation (1).

$$CB(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (1)$$

Let v represent the set of nodes, σ_{st} denote the total number of shortest paths from node s to node t, and $\sigma_{st}(v)$ signify the quantity of those pathways that traverse through v. this metric has many applications in network theory, tackling challenges in social networks, biological systems, transportation, and scientific collaboration.

- Degree centrality:

is the most direct and commonly employed metric of centrality. It measures the quantity of direct connections or edges a node possesses with other nodes in the network. In graph theory, the degree of a vertex denotes the quantity of edges associated with it. The degree centrality of a vertex (v) in a network comprising (n) vertices and (m) edges is delineated by the subsequent equation (2).

$$C_D(v) = \frac{\text{deg}(v)}{(n-1)} \quad (2)$$

- Closeness Centrality:

In a linked graph, the closeness centrality of a node quantifies its centrality inside the network, determined as the reciprocal of the cumulative length of the shortest paths from the node to all other nodes in the graph. Consequently, the more central a node is, the nearer it is to all other nodes. The

closeness centrality of a vertex v in a graph with n vertices is defined by the equation (3).

$$C_C(v) = \frac{1}{\sum d(v,i)} \quad (3)$$

For any i, where d(v, i) represents the shortest distance from v to i, all metrics of centrality are enumerated in Fig. 2.

Fig2. Different type of centralities

B. Traffic factors:

- Density:

Often represent the number of vehicles present in a particular area or road segment. A high density of vehicles indicates a large number of vehicles within a confined space, whereas a low density signifies fewer vehicles in the same space [16]. In the Fig3 we can see at the right low density area otherwise in the left there is a high density intersection with great number of vehicles. Density is an important factor in VANETs as it can affect the performance of communication protocols and routing protocols.

Fig3. Various mode of density at intersection

- Popularity:

Isn't a standard term in VANET research, it could be interpreted as the frequency of use or the amount of traffic that an intersection or road segment experiences. A popular road segment or intersection would be one that is frequently used by vehicles [18]. This could be measured in terms of the number of vehicles that pass through the intersection or road segment in a given time period.

- *Traffic flow:*

Refers to the movement of vehicles within the network. This flow is a complex process affected by several factors, including vehicle density, speed, direction, and the communication between vehicles (V2V) as well as between vehicles and infrastructure (V2I).

- *Speed:*

It means the velocity at which vehicles are moving within the network. The speed of vehicles in a VANET is a critical parameter as it influences several aspects of the network, the speed of vehicles can affect the communication between nodes. For instance, if vehicles are moving fast, the time during which two vehicles are within communication range of each other could be short.

- *Vehicle arrival rate:*

Typically refers to the volume of traffic entering a designated zone or roadway within a specific timeframe. This could be measured in vehicles per second, vehicles per minute, or vehicles per hour, depending on the context. In the Fig4 the vehicle arrival rate is equal to $2veh/T_2$ where T_2 represents the unit of time.

Fig4. Vehicle arrival rate per unit of time

The rate at which vehicles arrive in a VANET can fluctuate significantly, influenced by factors like the time of day, which day within the week, climatic conditions, and unique events.

- *Accident rate:*

The accident rate in VANET is a measure of how often accidents occur in a given area or time period, using data collected from vehicular communication.

The accident rate can be calculated using different methods, such as the number of accidents per vehicle-kilometer, the number of accidents per vehicle-hour, or the number of accidents per population.

C. *Economic factors:*

- *Profit point:*

These points are: Real Estate Development, Tourism and Hospitality, Technology and Innovation Hubs, Financial Services, Manufacturing and Logistics, Healthcare and Biotechnology deploying RSUs at them can indeed enhance economic growth.

D. *geometry factors:*

- *Constrained Delaunay Triangulation :*

Is a geometric algorithm used to create a triangulation of a set of points while respecting specified constraints, in [3] they apply this algorithm with some constraints, the following Figure Fig5 shows how can we apply this method.

- *Voronoi Diagram:*

A plane is divided into regions using Voronoi diagrams

Fig5. CDT algorithm in urban area.

according to how far away from a collection of points (sites) it is. Every area includes every point that is closest to a certain location, the authors in [19] used this method to deploy RSUs we can observe this partition in Fig6.

Fig6. Voronoi diagram in urban area.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Information has been collected from some related work and tabulated in table 1, and we tried to extract the relationship between the factors, objectives and the locations for deployment.

for all the objectives mentioned in the table 1 we can see that the choice of initial locations has been in both of intersection and road-segment, except that in the profit objective when we have seen that the choice has been in road-segment only.

In the same objective, we can see that the factors are different from study to another and this is return to the location type, as example in [7] they use the traffic flow as factor to minimize the delay while in [12] they use the accident rate, also they differ in factor selection although they use the same location and we can see this in [7] and [4].

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE STUDY

Study reference	Objective	Location	Connection Mode	Factors
[5]	Maximize the coverage	Intersection	I2V	-Closeness centrality. -Degree centrality.
[9]			V2I	-Communication range
[1]			V2I	-Popularity -Density -Communication range
[15]		Road segment	V2V V2I	-Probability of connectivity -Accident rate
[3]		Distinct location	V2I	-Achieved CDT
[7]	Minimize the delay	Road-segment	V2V V2I	-Low traffic
[4]				
[13]			V2V V2I	-Bus stop -Commercial activity -Accident rate
[6]		Intersection	V2V V2I	-Vehicle arrival rate -Transmission range -Road-segment length
[12]			V2V V2I	-Accident rate
[14]	Maximize the profit	Road-segment	V2I V2V	-Most profitable point along the road
[8]			I2V	
[10]	Multi Objectives	Intersection	V2V V2I	-Communication range
[11]				
[2]		Road-segment	V2V V2I	-Traffic demands

During each deployment process we may find two steps of location choice initial and final:

- Initial locations:

In this step the placement may be randomly or with specific factors, as example in (GICA) the authors decide to

with the same objective and the location type, we have observed that the factors are different from research to another, as example to that to maximize the coverage, the authors in [5] choose the Closeness and the degree centrality unlike those in [1] where they select the intersections with high density and more popularity for initial positions.

- Final locations:

To make decision in the end, the placement is based on factors that meet the desired objectives; the authors in [1] as mentioned in the first step have selected the overlapped area as factor to make final decision for placement for the purpose of achieving the maximum coverage area with high density.

Fig7. Location type compared to deployment objectives

When we see the Fig 7 we can notice the superiority of location type among others in the same objective, to maximize the coverage the authors are based in intersections location by three study, while we see one study in both of road-segment and distinct location, in delay optimization we have two study in intersection and three study in road-segment, the authors concentrates in road-segment by using both of connection mode V2V and V2I, the only solution to maximize the profit have been at road-segment, when the authors formulate the deployment in multi objective problem the choice was by two study and one study in intersection and road-segment respectively.

We can draw a clear relationship between objective of deployment and type of Location. If the objective is to maximize the coverage, it is preferable to deploy RSU at intersections and distinct places to confront the problem of uneven terrain such as bumps and potholes. On the other hand, if we want to reduce delay, it is advisable to choose roads instead of intersections. When we want to maximize the profit, it is also preferable to rely on roads. If there are multiple deployment objectives, intersections play the ideal role in this case. When choosing a location, you must pay attention to the factor that distinguishes it. For example, intersections have a group of factors such as density, popularity, centrality, and traffic flow, etc... We find other factors in roads, such as speed rate, density, number of accidents, length, probability of connectivity, etc..., so there is an indirect relationship linking the objective to the factor.

For example, if we want to maximize coverage, we will choose intersections as places, but those that have higher

density and a greater degree of centrality, instead of others that have lower density and degree of centrality. If we want to reduce delay, we will choose roads that are characterized by a lower probability of connectivity factor and lower density. Therefore, the location is characterized by a factor controlled by the objectives of placement.

The research gap extracted from the comparative study is that more than one factor can be used for the same type of location and we can support this suggestion by taking as example the studies in [5] and [1] where the factors are the centrality and the density respectively, so we can integrate with them to enhance the weight of intersection location to maximize the coverage.

We can summarize the relations mentioned above by the following scheme in Fig8.

Fig8. Relation of Objectives, Location and Factors in RSU deployment.

V. LIMITATIONS

Despite the promising outcomes of this study, certain limitations must be acknowledged to fully understand the research setting and its significance.

- **Streamlined Representation:**

The study's models may not have sufficiently addressed the intricacies of real traffic scenarios; although the simulations offer useful insights, they rely on specific assumptions and simplifications that may not be universally applicable. Subsequent research should focus on integrating more realistic traffic models to enhance the precision and veracity of the findings.

- **Disregard for Technological Progress:**

The study neglects to account for recent technological advancements, including the implementation of 5G, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence networks, which could substantially influence the efficacy and pertinence of the proposed solutions.

VI. CONCLUSION

In our work, we have relied on several factors to deploy the RSUs some of them rely on traffic and the other on network, economic and geometry, we have observed that the authors differed in choosing deployment factors despite the similarity of goals. While they not based on other factors, also we have concluded that there is a direct relation between objectives and locations, and an indirect relation between objectives and factors we can say that the selection of location related directly by the factors and the choice of factors is based on both of objectives and location.

We will try to integrate between existing factors or employ others that they do not apply before in our future research and analyze their effectively to maximize the goal and improve the network's performance.

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